

Individual Coursework 2 Report on

Laser Powder Bed Fusion in GE LEAP Fuel Nozzle

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Date – 29th November 2025.

Module

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(AUT2 25-26)**

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Laser Powder Bed Fusion and its Application in GE LEAP Fuel Nozzle

The GE LEAP fuel nozzle, shown in figure 1, is a flagship example of successful metal additive manufacturing (AM) implementation in the aerospace industry. GE Aviation announced in 2015 that the next LEAP engine would incorporate nearly 20 3D-printed fuel nozzles. The integration of AM allowed for substantial performance improvements and design simplification [1]. The resulting component is 25% lighter and stronger than the original nozzle. Crucially, it contributes to boosting the engine's fuel efficiency by up to 15% compared to the CFM56 engines [2]. Furthermore, LPBF enabled a major reduction in complexity: the fuel nozzles were reported to be five times more durable than the previous model and reduced the component count from 25 separate parts down to a single piece or assembly of five parts [3]. GE leads the industry in AM volume and machine capacity, having printed over 100,000 parts by 2020 [1].

Figure 1: GE LEAP fuel nozzle [4].

Components destined for the hot sections of aeroengines, such as the LEAP fuel nozzle, require materials with superior performance under extreme conditions [5]. The nickel-based superalloy Inconel 718 (IN718) is the most common alloy utilized in the aerospace industry for these high-temperature applications due to its mechanical strength at elevated temperatures [2] shown in Table 1. The microstructure of IN718 consists of the γ (gamma) matrix phase. Its mechanical properties rely heavily on precipitation hardening, primarily through the metastable γ'' (gamma double prime) phase, which provides excellent high-temperature strength [6].

Table 1: Functional Requirements and Material Properties

Property	Metric
Operating Temperature Capability	Close to melting point, 1336 °C [7]
Matrix Phase Stability	High phase stability (Face-Centred-Cubic nickel matrix) [1]
Primary Strengthening Phases	γ' and γ'' nano-precipitates (precipitation strengthened) [6]
Application Environment	High thermal stability and thermal oxidation resistance [8]

Manufacturing the intricate geometry of a modern fuel nozzle using traditional methods presents significant challenges. Conventional techniques like casting or forging struggles with complex geometries, consuming more time or being incapable of achieving structures like conformal cooling channels [5].

Advanced alloys like nickel and titanium superalloys are difficult and expensive to machine due to their natural tendency for work hardening [1]. The conventional manufacturing route for superalloy components, such as turbine blades, involves numerous complex steps—including investment casting and precision machining—which result in substantial material waste. Historically, only about 10% of the initial superalloy feedstock might end up in the final component [5]. The inherent difficulty in machining and the high material waste associated with conventional processes make the manufacturing cost prohibitive and the complexity difficult to manage.

Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF), shown in figure 2, also known as selective laser melting (SLM), is a prominent metal additive manufacturing (AM) technology [2].

Figure 2: Schematic of a typical LPBF machine [9].

Figure 3: Schematic of direct energy deposition processes [10].

LPBF enables complex geometries to be produced directly from a digital model [12]. This process is favoured over other AM processes like Directed Energy Deposition (DED), shown in figure 3, due to its high resolution and ability to produce high-quality metal parts shown in Table 2. LPBF drastically reduces material wastage, sometimes yielding waste levels as low as $\sim 5\%$ [1].

Table 2: Comparative Advantages of LPBF (L-PBF) over DED (L-DED)

Feature	L-PBF (Typical)	L-DED (Typical)
Process Control/Accuracy	High resolution and accuracy [1]	Generally, very low resolution, rough surface [1]
Component Count Reduction	High (e.g., 25 parts to 5 for nozzle) [1]	Moderate (often used for repair work) [1]
Cooling Rate	High ($\sim 10^4 - 10^6$ K/s) [13]	Lower (~ 100 x different than L-PBF) [6]
As-Built Hardness (IN718)	Higher (323.4 to 342.6 HV) [6]	Lower (246.4 to 276.4 HV) [6]
Laser Parameters	Smaller beam (~ 1 x magnitude difference); $P \leq 500$ W [13]	Larger beam; $P \geq 2$ x L-PBF power [6]

LPBF involves scanning a laser beam (with spot sizes around $20 - 100 \mu\text{m}$) across fine powder layers (thickness $\leq 100 \mu\text{m}$) at high speeds ($\sim 0.05 - 4$ m/s). Physics of this process dictates extreme thermal conditions [14].

When the temperature of the material exceeds its boiling point, the process shifts from conduction mode (shallow, rounded melt pool shown in figure 4) to keyhole mode. Keyhole mode is characterized by the laser fluence causing vaporization and generating sufficient recoil pressure to depress the liquid metal surface, forming a deep, high aspect ratio vapor cavity [14].

Figure 4: Evolutions of melt pool and vapor depression under stationary laser illumination [15].

The formation of the keyhole is crucial because it dramatically enhances laser energy absorption. This occurs due to multiple reflections of the laser beam inside the depression, allowing the laser energy to transfer more efficiently to the powder layer [16]. For example, simulations show that as laser power increases beyond the 110W threshold, shown in figure 5, the nominal absorptivity sharply increases due to keyhole formation and ray-entrapment. The resulting melt pool is subject to steep thermal gradients and high cooling rates ($\sim 10^4 - 10^6$ K/s) [14].

Figure 5: (a) plot of nominal absorptivity and energy gain versus input laser power. (b) and (c) show melt pool morphology for P80 and P200 cases, respectively [16].

Despite its advantages, LPBF introduces intrinsic defects, given in Table 3, that can badly deteriorate the part's performance, particularly relevant for safety-critical components like fuel nozzles [12].

Figure 6: Longitudinal view showing the free surface along with porosity distribution[16].

A detailed parametric study on Ti6Al4V confirmed that increasing laser power above a certain threshold (e.g., from 110W to 140W) rapidly transitions the process to the unstable keyhole regime, sharply increasing the melt pool volume (from 1.8x to 5x relative to 50W) and initiating porosity formation, shown in figure 6. The frequency and size of keyhole pores are highly dependent on the process parameters[16].

Table 3: LPBF Process Defects and Their Effects

Defect Type	Cause	Characteristics	Numerical Data (Ti6Al4V)
Lack-of-Fusion Porosity	Insufficient heat input; incomplete melting [5]	Irregular shape, large size; reduced density [8]	N/A (occurs at low power)
Keyhole Porosity	Excessive heat input; unstable keyhole collapse [14]	Spherical, small size; detriment to fatigue life [13]	35 – 95 μm diameter [16]

Solidification Cracking	Rapid cooling/solidification traps liquid between dendrites [5]	Jagged, located primarily at grain boundaries; length [5]	IN718/GH3536 highly susceptible [5]
Liquation Cracking	Remelting of low-melting-point phases (e.g., carbides) at grain boundaries [5]	Weakens grain boundaries under tensile stress [5]	Observed via low-melting-point carbides [5]

Mitigation strategies involve stringent process control and essential post-processing steps, particularly for high-value applications like the LEAP fuel nozzle. Choosing suitable surface enhancement techniques is based on cost and time effectiveness. While traditional mechanical methods rank highest in terms of lowest overall cost, LSP is advantageous for high-temperature service environments because high cold work (induced by traditional methods like shot peening) relaxes rapidly. Appropriate post-processing, given in Table 4, ensures the material properties of AM IN718 are comparable to wrought counterparts, providing necessary confidence for commercial use [1].

Table 4: Post-Processing Techniques

Post-Treatment	Mechanism	Application/Numerical Detail
Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP)	Annihilates microcracks and internal pores [2]	GH3536: 1050 °C at 100MPa for 3 h reduced crack/pore volume fraction from 0.96% to 0.08% [5]
Solid Solution Heat Treatment (SSHT)	Eliminates carbides; improves alloying element solid solution [5]	GH3536: 1080 °C for 0.5 h; enhanced tensile strength and ductility [5]
Laser Shock Peening (LSP)	Imparts deep compressive residual stress for surface enhancement [1]	IN718: Induces low cold work (1 – 6%), beneficial at high temperatures (Shot peening ~30%) [1]

The adoption of LPBF for the GE LEAP fuel nozzle is justified by the technology’s capacity to achieve previously impossible engineering metrics while controlling cost drivers [2].

LPBF enables significant cost reduction and performance enhancements by complexity and consolidation, performance, sustainability and cost. The capability to manufacture complex internal geometries (like the fuel delivery channels) as a single component reduces the part count from 25 to 5 (or a single piece) [5]. The resulting nozzle offers a 5-fold increase in durability and contributes to a 15% improvement in fuel burn efficiency [2]. By using layer-wise fabrication, LPBF substantially reduces raw material wastage (often ~ 5% waste, compared to ~ 90% waste in conventional superalloy production) [1].

This integration transforms the supply chain, enabling on-demand and on-site manufacturing, thus reducing inventory and downtime. The LPBF process, coupled with essential post-processing (HIP and SSHT) to mitigate inherent defects like cracking and porosity, successfully yields components that meet stringent aerospace requirements, thus enabling critical industrial success [5].

Appendix A

Article: Advances in metal additive manufacturing: A review of common processes, industrial applications, and current challenges [2]

This source provides a comprehensive look at the state of metal Additive Manufacturing (AM), outlining common processes, applications, and challenges. Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) dominates the market, holding 54% of the metal AM market share in 2020. Other major categories include Directed Energy Deposition (DED) and Material/Binder Jetting, each holding 16%. Key industrial adopters include automotive (20% of AM revenue) and aerospace (18%). Metal AM offers significant benefits, such as reducing lead times by up to 70% and decreasing mass by 35% or more in aerospace components. However, adoption is challenged by the lack of widely accepted technical standards, which are primarily being developed by ISO and ASTM. Testing and Qualifications account for 30% of under-development standards. The high cost, often ranging from USD 115,000 to USD 1.9 million for equipment, also limits implementation.

Appendix B

Article: Keyhole fluctuation and pore formation mechanisms during laser powder bed fusion additive manufacturing [13]

This source uses in situ synchrotron X-ray imaging to reveal keyhole fluctuation (2.5 – 10 kHz) and pore formation mechanisms in Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF). Pores, which are detrimental to fatigue life, can form in a newly discovered transition regime (II), initiating at the rear keyhole wall, unlike the typical bottom formation in the unstable regime (III). The Front Keyhole Wall (FKW) angle collapses to a single function of the Normalised Enthalpy Product for various alloys, providing a non-dimensional threshold for predicting keyhole stability transitions. Vapour bubbles undergo rapid, pressure-driven growth (volume increases $\sim t^3$), followed by shrinkage via condensation, which is critically slowed by concurrent hydrogen diffusion.

Appendix C

Article: Laser melting modes in metal powder bed fusion additive manufacturing [14]

The source critically reviews metal Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) by establishing rigorous process-based definitions for melting modes (conduction, transition, keyhole). This is achieved using in situ high-speed synchrotron X-ray imaging, which provides sub nanosecond temporal resolution. LPBF involves extreme thermal conditions, characterized by heating/cooling rates up to 10^8 K/s and peak thermal gradients of 10^8 K/m. The stable-keyhole mode is highlighted as essential for efficient and robust manufacturing because it substantially enhances laser absorption via multiple reflections. Conversely, unstable keyholes cause defects like porosity and extremely fast spatter (>40 m/s in Ti-6Al-4V). The mode transitions are quantitatively defined by changes in melt pool depth-to-width aspect ratio over time.

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